

EXTRACTION OF POTASH FROM FELSPAR. PART VIII. STRUCTURE OF FELSPAR

BY ESHWAR RAJ SAXENA AND D. S. DATAR

CENTRAL LABORATORIES FOR SCIENTIFIC & INDUSTRIAL RESEARCH, HYDERABAD-DN.

(Received June 22, 1955)

The structural formula of felspar molecule, as suggested, is based upon the experimental data obtained by the authors and the X-ray data.

The term felspar is a family name for a large variety of very common minerals. In composition, they are aluminosilicates of potassium, sodium or calcium and their mixtures. The general formula for felspar^o can be represented as $RO \cdot Al_2O_3 \cdot 6SiO_2$, where R stands for 2K, 2Na, Ca, etc.

The fundamental unit in building the silicate minerals is the SiO_4 group, consisting of one silicon atom surrounded by four oxygens¹. The oxygens are arranged at the four corners of a regular tetrahedron, with the silicon at its centre. These silicate groups can occur separately or may be linked together in a number of ways by sharing oxygen atoms with adjacent groups, thus forming more complex structures. Besides, the structures are built up by sharing of the free valencies by other atoms like magnesium, aluminium etc. Felspar comes under the 'Framework' structures, which are three dimensional networks, formed when each tetrahedron is linked by all four oxygens of the corners to other tetrahedra.

It is a well known fact that the structural characteristics of a mineral group contribute to the physical and physico-chemical properties of the mineral. In many cases the knowledge of the structure enables one to explain quite clearly the observed behaviour of the mineral. This inspired several of the scientists to investigate the structure of felspar. The main basis for the structure to be suggested was generally the similarity of the properties of felspar, mica and kaolin and their inter-conversions of one into other. Clark² represented the structural formulae of orthoclase, mica and China clay as follows :

The formulae are satisfactory so far as conversion of mica into China clay is concerned, but they cannot explain the conversion of felspar into mica which involves a drastic change in the acid radical. Scharizer tried to overcome this difficulty by representing orthoclase as potassium dialumino-hexasilicate.

Mellor and Holdcroft⁴ similarly represented the felspar and clay structures in the following manner :

Denaeyer and Jakob⁵ applied the theory of co-ordination to the constitution of felspar. They regarded that the formula of the type $\text{K. SiO}_3. \text{SiO}_2. \text{SiO}_4. \text{Al}$ to be wrong because of the difference in the behaviour of aluminium and potassium. They regarded felspar as a salt of the monobasic acid:

Niggli⁶ represented felspar (albite) by $[\text{Al.}(\text{SiO}_4. \text{SiO}_2. \text{SiO}_2)_3]_{\text{Na}_3}^{\text{Al}_3}$

Machatschki⁷ based the felspar structure on a framework of united silicon tetrahedron (SiO_4) and aluminium tetrahedron (AlO_4) with the cations K, Na and Ca situated in the interstices of the negatively charged framework of tetrahedra. He was the first person to postulate this type of structure. He ascribed the difference between orthoclase and plagioclase to the former containing large cations and the latter having small cations. It is significant to note that the further study by X-ray has essentially corroborated the suggestions made by Machatschki some 25 years ago. The X-ray study has contributed considerably to the determination of crystal structure of minerals like felspar,

Kozu, Eudo and Harding⁸ did some work on the symmetry of the feldspars containing K and Na. Schiebold⁹ made a number of measurements which established the unit cells and space groups of various feldspars.

The first determination of atomic arrangement in feldspar was made by Taylor¹⁰. He has shown that feldspars which belong to monoclinic system (orthoclase) are built in a certain general type of structure, which he calls as 'orthoclase' structure. The most striking feature of this structure¹¹ is a peculiar type of chains, which are linked by sharing of oxygen atoms to other chains on all sides so that the whole structure is a three dimensional network of linked tetrahedra. The chains run parallel to the axis a (100) of the crystal. The main cleavages $c(001)$ and $b(010)$ are parallel to the chains, since the strongest binding is along them.

X-ray analysis shows that all feldspars have the same structural scheme of limited tetrahedra and that the cations are situated in the interstices in corresponding places. In orthoclase and other feldspars of the monoclinic system, either they are perfectly monoclinic or there is a slight departure from monoclinic symmetry. But in the case of plagioclase, the symmetry is distorted so much as to convert the monoclinic into triclinic system.

This distortion may be ascribed to the smaller sizes of Na or Ca ions which allow the tetrahedra to close in somewhat around the cavity in which the ions are placed. This movement of tetrahedra destroys the symmetry planes and rotation axes present in monoclinic system. According to Taylor¹² the reason for the distortion in the symmetry of orthoclase (monoclinic) and albite (triclinic) is also the same. Certain oxygen atoms in the tetrahedra come very near the alkali atoms.

According to his measurements the distances are as follows: In orthoclase the distance between K and six O is 2.85Å and between K and four O is 3.10Å. In albite the distance between Na and five O is 2.5, 2.55, 2.6, 2.65, 2.7Å and Na and three O is 2.9, 3.4, 3.8Å.

It will be seen that the potassium atom has ten oxygen atoms around it at approximately equal distances, whereas the sodium atom is surrounded by a group of 6, or at most 7 oxygen atoms.

The suggested structure of feldspar.—The structural formula to be assigned to orthoclase should be based upon the following facts.

(1) The structure consists of chains which are linked by sharing of oxygen atoms to other chains on all sides so that the whole structure is a three dimensional network of tubed tetrahedra.

(ii) X-ray analysis fails to distinguish Al from Si atoms. One quarter of the atoms at the centres of the tetrahedron in an unit cell is Al and the remainder, Si. This structure will be obtained by the replacement of Si^{4+} by Al^{3+} . As Al^{3+} has got a lower charge than Si^{4+} , a difference in ionic charge is created. To make the structure electrically neutral, a cation must be added. The position of K in the structural formula may be near Al.

(iii) Each K atom has six O neighbours at $2.85\text{\AA}$ and four at $3.1\text{\AA}$; that is, there are ten O atoms at the average distance of about $3\text{\AA}$ from each K atom.

(iv) In view of the great resistance of the felspar to the reactants, reactions of felspar are unaccompanied by any side reactions; that is why although these reactions in solid state are heterogeneous, they occur in a definite manner, and it is possible to study them quantitatively and to correlate the data obtained. In the acid reactions of orthoclase^{18,14} it is observed that orthoclase molecule is decomposed and potassium and aluminium are liberated simultaneously and in equimolar amounts. It is further seen that the potassium and aluminium atoms are protected by silica groups around them and these are accessible to reactants (acid and salts) only after four out of six silica groups in the orthoclase molecule are separated by the action of alkali or alkaline earth oxide with the formation of $3\text{RO} \cdot \text{SiO}_2$, where R stands for two alkali atoms or one alkaline earth atom. It is obvious from the above that in the structural formula for $\text{K}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 6\text{SiO}_2$, K_2O and Al_2O_3 should be together and 6SiO_2 around them, probably three groups of silica on each side. When two groups of silica are on each side, that is, altogether four out of six are removed, the residual arrangement is less resistant to the action of reactants than the original felspar.

The structural formula of the residual molecule may be represented as :

In this structure, hereafter called ring structure, the above-mentioned conditions are satisfied, viz., (i) when this structure is decomposed, both K_2O and Al_2O_3 will come out simultaneously and in equimolar amounts; (ii) the structure is electrically neutral; (iii) there are ten oxygen atoms surrounding each K atom, six out of them being at a slightly nearer distance than the remaining four (marked 7,8,9,10); (iv) the potassium and

ring structure of the felspar molecule. When 4 CaO replace the 4 OH in the kaolin molecule, the resulting product, which is similar in composition to the product (obtained when felspar is heated with calcium oxide), is readily decomposed by dilute acids with the formation of aluminium salt. It will be of interest to note here that on heating felspar with sodium carbonate or sodium sulphate and treating the residue with water, potassium in felspar molecule comes out as potassium hydroxide and the remaining insoluble matter has the same composition as kaolin.

Grateful thanks of the authors are due to Dr. S. Husain Zaheer, for his continued interest and guidance in this investigation.

R E F E R E N C E S

1. Hauth (Jr.), *Amer. Ceram. Soc. Bull.*, 1951, 30, 5.
2. Clark, *Bull. U.S. Geol. Sur.*, 1895, 125.
3. Scharizer, *Z. Kryst.*, 1894, 22, 369.
4. Mello[†] et al., *Trans. Ceram. Soc.*, 1911, 10, 94.
5. Denaeys et al., *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1922, 31, 131.
6. Niggli, *Lehrbuch der Mineralogie*, 1920, p. 379.
7. Machatschki, *Ctbl. Min.*, 1928, 97A.
8. Kozu et al., *Sci. Rep. Tohoku*, 1924, 3.
9. Schiebold, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1929, 25, 316.
10. Taylor, *Lunds. Univ. Arsk.*, 1921, 17, No. 6.
11. Bragg, "Atomic Structure of Minerals", p. 1937, 231.
12. Taylor, *Z. Krist.*, 1933, 85, 425.
13. Saxena & Datar, *this Journal*, 1954, 17, 44.
14. *Idem, ibid.* (under publication).